

A Comprehensive Survey and Comparative Analysis of Black Hole attack in Mobile Ad Hoc Network

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Abstract : A Mobile Ad-hoc Network (MANET) is a self managing network consists of versatile nodes that are capable of communicating with each other without having any fixed infrastructure. These nodes may be routers and/or hosts. Due to this dynamic nature of the network, routing protocols are vulnerable to various kinds of attacks. The black hole attack is one of the conspicuous security threats in MANETs. As the route discovery process is obligatory and customary, attackers make use of this loophole to get success in their motives to destruct the network. In Black hole attack the packet is redirected to a node that actually does not exist in the network. Many researchers have proposed different techniques to detect and prevent this type of attack. In this paper, we have analyzed various routing protocols in this context. Further we have shown a critical comparison among various protocols. We have shown various routing metrics are required proper and significant analysis of the protocol.

Keywords : Black Hole, MANET, Performance Parameters, Routing Protocol

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